

PERFECTING THE ARTISTIC IMAGE IN CONTEMPORARY YOUTH PROSE

Ulkanboeva Matluba Hasanboy qizi

Doctoral candidate of the Institute of Uzbek Language,
Literature and Folklore, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15639397>

Abstract. This article addresses the expression of creative vision through associative imagery in Uzbek short stories. The study analyzes the gradual development of associative imagery as a literary tradition in our national literature. Specifically, it examines the artistic interpretation of images such as the monkey, the bull, and the pomegranate in Abdulla Qahhor's stories, along with their symbolic and figurative content. Additionally, the use of these images in the stories of contemporary young writers, enriched with new, relevant meanings, is analyzed on a scientific basis.

Keywords: short story, image, associative image, creative vision, artistic interpretation.

Introduction. A short story is not merely a narration of interesting events; it is a new artistic reality that expresses the writer's creative concept, their attitude towards social reality, and their conclusions, in which the author's important views on existence are embedded. This is why creativity is, first and foremost, considered wisdom. Since the short story, like other works of art, thinks through images and details, one of the current tasks of literary studies is to examine and analyze the artistic and aesthetic function of images and details in modern Uzbek short stories and the experience of young prose writers in using them.

Literature review on the topic. In Uzbek literary studies, there are numerous research works related to the study of artistic images in short stories. In particular, Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor M. Kuchkarova, in her articles "A Man Talking to Himself" and "Elements of Neo-mythologism in the Stories of Nurilla Chori," dedicated to the work of young writer Nurilla Chori, offers a new interpretation of artistic images in Ahmad A'zam's fictional world. Another well-known scholar, D. Kuronov, in his articles "A Work Written with Inspiration," "A Bunch from My Pleasure," and "Two Words in Defense of the Thief," presents well-founded conclusions about the composition and imagery of stories.

Analyzing one of Nurillo Chori's literary characters, M. Kuchkarova draws attention to a subtle detail related to this character: "But the uncle is alive. He changed his name associated with 'Allah' (Khudoykul) to Urak (axe). One can

sense how skillfully the writer provides subtle hints about the tragedies of the historical social epoch. During the Soviet era, the symbol of the working-peasant class was the "SICKLE AND AXE." [3] The scholar's approach to the artistic detail related to the change in the main character's name allows for new conclusions in literary studies.

Furthermore, in D. Quronov's article "A Work Written with Inspiration," new, well-founded conclusions are drawn regarding the story "Horror" and its interpretations. The article discusses literary caution formed under the influence of the despotic regime. Our people have a saying: "One who has been burned by milk blows on yogurt." The subsequent generation, for whom the bitter fate of creators such as A. Fitrat, A. Qodiriy, and Chulpan served as an example, could not openly express their creative concepts. Certainly, A. Qahhor understands very well how difficult the task is because, as they say, "a person bitten by a snake fears a striped rope." He witnessed those who suffered during that time and saw that many people still cannot recover. The writer recalls the legend of an elephant that was chained to an iron stake for 200 years, and after the chain rotted, it circled around the stake for another hundred years. He says: "The elephant is a mindless animal, so why can't we move far from the stake driven in by the cult era?" The writer deeply feels that the horror instilled in people's hearts by the era of repression has not yet departed, and its departure will not be easy. [4;31] Indeed, due to the fear of repression, the artist could not openly express his condition or the state of the nation and found a solution in the mysterious artistic world of verbal art. For this very reason, at the beginning of the 20th century, literature began to create images specifically selected to express creative intentions. These were encoded images that conveyed the author's true state. In literary studies, there is a concept of associative image. In the dictionary compiled under the guidance of Professor D. Quronov, it is given the following definition: "Associative image (lat. associatio - to unite, to connect) is an image based on difficult-to-access connections between objects, phenomena, and concepts, arising through their unexpected connection (comparison, juxtaposition, contrast) and thereby acquiring a high degree of metaphorical and subjective quality. Essentially, associativity is a characteristic inherent in the nature of any image. That is, the associative image is not a special type of artistic image; this term refers to an image that strongly demonstrates the associativity inherent in the artistic image as a whole. Consequently, there is a certain conventionality in the application of the term. The associative image demands creative activity from the reader, the ability to perceive the

connections between the objects and phenomena on which the author relies, a chain of connections." [5;38] In the dictionary, the associative image is interpreted more in relation to genres of the lyrical type: "In modern poetry, which strives for metaphorical perception of the world, associative images occupy an increasingly large place, and numerous examples can be cited." [5;39] The images we analyzed below and their interpretations show that strongly associated images are also found in prose, particularly in short stories. We would like to emphasize that such associative images were created with the desire to remain faithful to the great truth, while simultaneously protecting oneself from the winds of repression. Uzbek writers of the 20th century used a special way of expressing spiritual suffering and the pain of society, and this tradition continued in the works of subsequent literary generations.

Research Methodology The article is based on sociological, biographical, and comparative-historical methods.

Analysis and Results

In A. Qahhor's stories, there are several associative images. The images of the monkey in "The Horror," the bull in "The Thief," and the pomegranate in "The Pomegranate" are among those that serve to express specific literary and aesthetic intentions. So, with which realities of their time do these images connect and harmonize? It is known that in Uzbek neighborhoods, encountering monkeys in houses is an unusual phenomenon. This unusualness raises several questions for the reader: Why did the writer introduce the image of a monkey? Why did the monkey grab Unsin by the shoulder? If we remove the monkey from the story, a piece of horn flying in the wind could grab Unsin's shoulder, or a piece of cloth covering his face could give him an even more terrifying appearance, and logically, the story's plot could support such a detail. However, in that case, the writer would not have been able to achieve his intended goal or express his true artistic intention. The monkey is a concept foreign to the Uzbek mentality, an artistic expression of ideology. This indicates that the despotic regime, which tore the belief in the Creator from the consciousness of people who strictly followed Islamic laws and had firm faith in their hearts, promoted godlessness - atheism, and tried to convince people who firmly believed they were created from earth that humanity descended from apes. It attacked and destroyed national intellectuals like A. Fitrat, A. Qodiriy, and Cholpon. In his article "A Work Written with Inspiration," D. Quronov concludes that both Unsin and Nodirmohbegim represent A. Qahhor himself. In our view, Unsin, who strived for freedom and perished on this path, is a symbolic image created in

comparison with the bitter fate of the Jadid thinkers, while Nodirmohbegim, who drew conclusions from his death, struck the ground three times with her fist, and left the Dodkhoh's palace, is a generalized symbol of A. Qahhor and his contemporaries Oybek and G. Gulyam. Although these writers were forced to compromise with the ruling system, they left behind a legacy, placing their creative concepts alongside true literary masterpieces.

The image of the bull in the story "The Thief" is not used by chance. This image was created as a hint and irony towards the vices manifested in the nature of some of our compatriots during the writer's lifetime, such as submissiveness, obedience, and "conformity." The writer couldn't help but suffer from this vice in the character of his contemporaries and express it with bitter irony. The portrayal of this image alongside Qobil bobo served to more vividly manifest the writer's artistic concept.

In the story "The Pomegranate," the fruit - the pomegranate, chosen by a woman as a mysterious phenomenon, is also a symbolic image that points to truths that the writer could not express openly. The politics of that time did not allow A. Qahhor to speak frankly about the realities he understood. A well-known example of the pomegranate image is found in Uvaysi's work. The pain of the Khan's harem, one of the painful aspects of that time in Chistan, and the suffering of the young beautiful girls living there are beautifully expressed.

The image of the pomegranate used in the story evokes the pain of the totalitarian Soviet regime, as mentioned in the cleansing, through its blood and the fact that this blood is contained within a closed dome. A. Qahhor's mastery lies in the fact that the woman chose a pomegranate - a fruit that could express the spiritual pain of herself and her contemporaries - among various objects that could have been mysterious, and did not burn either a spindle or a kebab. Pointing to the true reality through such associative imagery is also found in other writers, but since the article's scope is limited, we will confine ourselves to the analysis presented above. This is because the true purpose of the article is to show that this literary tradition continues in the works of today's youth, that young prose writers are following in the footsteps of their predecessors by selecting special associative images for their stories.

The images of worms and insects used in the stories of Jasur Kengboyev "The Rattling Worm" and Javlon Jovliyev "The Tyrant's Insects" are among the associative images analyzed above.

Jasur Kengboyev's collection of stories "Khadik" was published recently. The very title of the book serves to express the author's attitude towards reality

and his conclusions. The endless stream of information directed at human consciousness allows certain dark forces to easily manipulate, control, and exploit human minds for their own benefit. Today, merely watching video content turns a person into someone's consumer. Any malicious movement can easily draw the younger generation into its fold. The current social and spiritual situation is extremely unstable. In other words, there is now fear in the minds of every intellectual and person who cares about the future of the nation. J. Kengbayev senses this and urges his readers to be extremely vigilant in the face of the information flow.

The image of the worm in Jasur Kengboev's story "The Nut Worm" symbolically represents destructive ideas that take root in people's minds and consume them, as well as ego-driven individuals who gain people's trust and sacrifice them for personal gain. The story consists of a scene where student Mahmudov confronts Professor Daminov, his trip to a walnut grove to prepare a report, and his conversation with a gardener. The writer doesn't preach or philosophize about kindness and goodness in the story. He uses the image of the nut worm so skillfully that the reader intuitively grasps the author's creative intent. This vivid expression of artistic intent through imagery, as mentioned earlier, demonstrates the successful continuation of the literary tradition inherent to the Uzbek short story school, passed down through generations. In the general dialogue, the author describes in detail how a gardener, upon meeting the student in the walnut grove, asks, "Tell the truth, who sent you here?" [2;35] and grows gloomy upon learning that no one had sent him. The writer reveals the reason for this despondency at the end of the story: "I heard three or four of our teachers whispering under the old mulberry tree where we were standing.

Domla Daminov didn't let one father into the house... The deceased lived in an abandoned garden of the metal factory...

"I was stunned, as if struck by lightning." According to the plot, a "worm" had entered Professor Daminov's heart. He neither took care of nor concerned himself with his elderly father. The father waits for news from a student who arrived by chance, suspecting: "Could my son have sent him?" The writer doesn't dwell on why Professor Daminov doesn't care for his father. Because there's no need for that. No strong reason can justify leaving an old father alone. An Uzbek child doesn't do that. This means that a worm has infected Professor Daminov's Uzbek identity and authenticity. Perhaps a vice, not inherent to our people's nature, in the form of a worm, entered the professor's heart and consciousness

as a result of the orders and propaganda of the former totalitarian regime and completely consumed him. The fact that the image of the "worm" can symbolize everything across all times serves the artistic maturity of the story.

In Javlon Jovliyev's story "The Insects of the Tyrant," the insect emerges as another new example of an associative image. The plot revolves around a student who has just finished his studies wandering in search of work and finally finding it. The author's true creative intention is manifested in three places in the story. Firstly, where the portrait of a department head producing various medicines against harmful insects is drawn: "The department head turned out to be a pleasant-looking, polite, frail-appearing man of about sixty. The skullcap on his head suited him very well... The elderly employee sat in a white coat, drinking green tea and listening to the song 'Urtar.'" [1;197] The description shows that the elderly employee lives in the Uzbek way. However, in this same employee's confession in the story - "Excuse me, my child, I can't write in Uzbek..." [1;199] - one can understand that the character who lives in the Uzbek way and strives to be Uzbek actually cannot reason in his native language, and no matter how hard he tries, he essentially cannot be Uzbek and remains in a suspended state. Another important passage that serves as a key to the author's artistic intent is evident in the narrator's father's speech: "Don't blame this person, understand," my father then said. "Maybe his parents aren't to blame for raising him this way. It was that time. That same atmosphere. The blame lies with the slaves of desire, my child! He also wants to live like an Uzbek. But colonial insects tried to destroy our roots, you hear, our roots. Language, religion, then nation. They couldn't achieve their goal. But they poisoned and destroyed the roots of many weak people. They made some of them sick for life." [1;200] Expressing true artistic intent with an open journalistic spirit, without hiding it in symbols, is characteristic of J. Jovliyev's style. Unlike J. Kengbayev, he openly expresses the meaning that the tyrant imposes on the image of insects, creating an individual symbolic image by comparing the ideas of the tyrannical regime, instilled in people's consciousness with the intention of forcing them to forget and destroy our language, religion, and national traditions, to a dangerous insect that has settled on the roots of plants. The elderly department head trying to preserve his sickly roots in J. Jovliyev's story, and J. Kengboyev's hero, Professor Daminov, whose national upbringing has been eaten by worms, are victims of years of colonial policy that have survived to this day.

Conclusions and Recommendations. The analysis demonstrates that studying artistic images in association with the realities of that time opens the way for new interpretations in literary studies. The artistic possibilities of a work can be expanded by using associative imagery not only in poetry but also in prose. Every image and detail in the story must be mobilized to express the writer's artistic intent. Associative images are distinguished by their special emphasis or uniqueness in the story. For example, particular attention is paid to the images of the bull, pomegranate, and insect, while the worm and monkey reveal their distinctiveness. Associative images, in their own right, are capable of expressing artistic intent; in the words of Professor Yu. Solijonov, they can be called "speech" images.

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